

PLAYERS INCREASE OVERALL AND SPECIAL PHYSICAL FITNESS IN TRAINING.

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Annotation: this article is a summary of how players can improve overall and specific physical fitness in training.

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INTRODUCTION

The decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a number of decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan were adopted in order to educate a competent generation in Uzbekistan, attract talented young people to sports, create conditions for further support and development of our national football, select young players, and ensure the deep development of professional skills and, it is envisaged to organize the process of training young players in accordance with international requirements for the development of modern football, to teach the general training of a football player based on scientific methodological recommendations. (Godik, W. N. Platonov, 1988).

The upbringing of highly qualified players in the game of football has always been considered an urgent problem. By increasing the level of training of highly qualified players in physical maturity, this sport is associated with the correct orientation of training from young people in the boarding schools of special specialized children's and Youth Olympic Reserve sports schools, children's and youth sports schools. The practitioner noted that in most players who are considered highly qualified in Uzbek football by specialists and coaches, technical and tactical actions are at a much lower level. A clear example of this is the conspicuous shortcomings of technical and tactical actions at international meetings of players playing in our national team.

The next stage of development of Uzbek football players is directly related to the development of young children and junior football. The more children and teenagers are trained, the more efficiently the training process is established, the more effective the development phase of our next football.

The physical fitness of the player is considered one of the important components of sports training, and a process aimed at the development of physical qualities – strength, endurance, dexterity, speed, agility, general lack of the player's physical fitness is the basis for respect for the results. This basically ensures the solution of the following tasks: 1. All-round harmonic development of the player's organism, increasing its functionality, developing physical qualities. 2. Increase your health level. 3. The correct use of active rest during intense training and nagruzka competition. General physical fitness sets the stage for special training.

That is, the necessary condition for maturation in the chosen sport-as a condition-ensures the comprehensive development of strength, agility, endurance, agility, agility.

In the sports literature published in recent years, great attention is paid to sports training as the key of the control of the physical movement of sports. Currently, tests are widely used in all sports. They are used in quick and intermediate control. On the football field, officials attach the greatest importance to assessing the physical fitness of players in different ways.

The game activity of players consists only in jumping, running and walking, their movement is very complex, they fight with an opponent, run at the greatest speed, complex tactical tasks are performed. Therefore, the physical training of players must be carried out in such a way that it takes into account the nature of their playing activities, so that this is the basis for improving their technical and tactical skills.

R. A. Akramov, A. A. Suchilin (1987) notes that the general training of the player is associated with other sports that have a general effect on the body of those who are engaged in comprehensive training of physical abilities, solving the tasks of increasing general working capacity and general development of exercises.

Lisenchuk G. A. (2003), Shamaradin V. N. (1997), Suchilin A. A. (1988) recognize that most of the exercises used to increase overall fitness have an all-round effect on the body, including long-term running in high low places, more endurance, short running distances, and gymnastic exercises aimed at increasing agility. In general physical training, the development and strengthening of the musculoskeletal system is achieved by improving the functioning of internal organs and systems, improving the Coordination of movements and increasing the overall level of quality of movement.

Many thinkers have recommended the development of certain techniques using mahsus exercises aimed at developing physical qualities, and for this, usually, according to the structure of the performance character, the yohud tehnik method uses mahsus exercises similar to its individual elements.

From a pedagogical point of view, physical fitness is divided into general and special physical fitness. General physical fitness (UJT) is the basis for special physical fitness that solves the aforementioned problems. The actor uses general developmental Gymnastics exercises performed with and without objects as the main means of general physical training, paired exercises with regular alternation of the intensity of the movements performed, action and Sports Games, relay races, crossovers. The physical ability of the player or his ability to move can be determined from the qualities of strength, agility, agility. Based on the improvement of physical qualities, it lies in the fact that the body is able to withstand repeated excesses, physical overloads from the level of its own working capacity.

At the initial preparatory stage in working with players, it is advisable to use a complex of tools aimed at acquiring comprehensive physical training, strengthening health and harmonic development, acquiring hilma-Hill skills and qualifications, training in the initial foundations of football game techniques and tactics.

The task of physical fitness at this time will first of all consist in the formation of the movement functions of the players (strength, speed, endurance, agility and dexterity, as well as being able to control their movements at intervals, in the air and according to the degree of muscle tension are the main components of the movement function).

Great attention should be paid to the upbringing of the speed of movement, since in childhood and adolescence there are ample opportunities for the upbringing of this most important physical quality.

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